

COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE FREQUENCY OF BRONCHIOLITIS IN BREAST FED AND BOTTLE FED INFANTS

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Abstract

Objective: To determine prevalence of breastfed and bottle-fed infants and to compare the frequency of bronchiolitis in infants aged 6 to 12 months on breast feed and bottle feed.

Study Design: Cross-Sectional Study.

Study Setting: Department of Pediatrics, Punjab Rangers Teaching, Lahore, Pakistan.

Study Duration: March to June 2025

Methodology: A total of 312 infants aged 6–12 months were enrolled using non-probability consecutive sampling. Infants were classified as breastfed or bottle-fed during the first six months of life, while bronchiolitis was diagnosed clinically on the basis of fever, tachypnea, and wheezing or crackles.

Results: Of the 312 infants, 85 (27.2%) were breastfed and 227 (72.8%) were bottle-fed. Bronchiolitis was present in 13 (15.3%) of breastfed infants and in 52 (22.9%) of bottle-fed infants. Although bronchiolitis was more frequent among bottle-fed infants, the difference was not statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 2.173$, $p = 0.140$). Stratified analysis across age and gender groups revealed similar patterns, with consistently higher frequencies of bronchiolitis among bottle-fed infants.

Conclusion: Breastfeeding demonstrated a protective trend against bronchiolitis, although the association was not statistically significant. Promoting exclusive breastfeeding during the first six months of life may serve as a simple, cost-effective strategy for reducing the burden of respiratory infections in infancy.

INTRODUCTION

Bronchiolitis is a common respiratory illness that primarily affects infants and young children under the age of 2 years. It is characterized by upper respiratory symptoms, such as rhinorrhea (runny nose), followed by lower respiratory infection and inflammation, leading to wheezing and/or crackles (rales).¹ The clinical presentation of bronchiolitis often includes fever, cough, and respiratory distress, accompanied by an increased respiratory

rate, retractions, wheezing, and crackles.^{2,3} The onset of bronchiolitis is typically preceded by one to three days of upper respiratory tract symptoms, such as nasal congestion and discharge. Viral infections are the primary cause of bronchiolitis, with the most common pathogen being the respiratory syncytial virus (RSV), followed by rhinovirus.⁴ Other less common viral causes include parainfluenza virus, human

metapneumovirus, influenza virus, adenovirus, coronaviruses, and human bocavirus.² RSV infection poses a global burden on children, and it is associated with severe respiratory illness in infants. Breastfeeding practices have been observed to play a protective role against severe RSV infection.⁵ Breastfeeding not only offers cost-effective prevention of respiratory illnesses in children but also provides them with immunity against various harmful organisms.⁶ Exclusive or partial breastfeeding has shown to reduce risk of bronchiolitis severity by 58% according to a multicenter prospective cohort study.⁷

Exclusive breastfeeding when contrasted with other modes of feeding has considerable impact in reducing respiratory illnesses like bronchiolitis.⁸ Moreover respiratory illnesses like bronchiolitis is more prevalent in infants receiving formula milk exclusively.⁹ Number of episodes of bronchiolitis reduce considerably in exclusive or partial breast feeding, therefore breast feeding programs should be promoted as a preventive measure in respiratory illnesses.¹⁰ In one study, the prevalence of exclusive breast feeding was 187/921 (20.3%) among cases and 275/719 (38.3%) among controls, overall 28.2%. Exclusive vs. partial breast feeding was associated with 48% reduced odds of bronchiolitis hospitalization with 95% confidence interval.

In the secondary analysis, exclusive vs. no breast feeding was associated with 58% reduced odds of bronchiolitis hospitalization (OR 0.42, 95% CI 0.23, 0.77), whereas predominant breast feeding (OR 0.77, 95% CI 0.37, 1.57) and occasional breast feeding (OR 0.98, 95% CI 0.57, 1.69) were not associated with meaningfully reduced odds of bronchiolitis hospitalization.⁷ In another study, results showed that regarding feeding at 4 months, exclusive breastfeeding reduced by 41% the number of episodes of bronchiolitis. In one study, infants were divided into 3 groups. Group 1 included those infants who were given formula 1 or STD formula (n=70) with lower proteins, group 2 received standard formula or INN (n=70) and group 3 (n=70) was exclusively breastfed (BFD group). Frequency of bronchiolitis in group 1 was 11.7%, 6% in group 2 and 5.7% in group 3.⁹

By conducting a rigorous comparative study on the frequency of bronchiolitis in breastfed and bottle-fed

infants, this research aims to contribute valuable insights into the role of infant feeding practices in respiratory health. Also there is scarcity of data available on above mentioned subject. The results of this study may inform healthcare recommendations for parents and caregivers, helping them make informed choices regarding infant nutrition.

METHODOLOGY:

This cross-sectional study was conducted in the Pediatric Department of Punjab Rangers Teaching Hospital, Lahore, after obtaining approval from the hospital's ethical committee and the College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan. The duration of the study was six months from March to June 2025, following ethical approval. A total of 312 infants were included, and the sample size was calculated using the WHO calculator with a 95% confidence interval, 5% margin of error, and an expected prevalence of exclusive breastfeeding of 28.2%. A non-probability consecutive sampling technique was employed for the recruitment of study participants.

Infants aged 6 to 12 months presenting for routine checkups were included in the study, provided that informed consent was obtained from their mothers. Children born with congenital heart disease or with pre-existing respiratory conditions were excluded. Operational definitions were strictly applied: infants were labeled as exclusively breastfed or bottle-fed according to their feeding practices during the first six months of life, while bronchiolitis was defined as the presence of low-grade fever (99–101°F), tachypnea (>30/min), and an episode of wheezing or crackles on auscultation. Data collection was carried out through structured proformas. Each infant meeting the inclusion criteria was assessed and classified as breastfed or bottle-fed based on history. The diagnosis of bronchiolitis was confirmed and labeled according to the operational definition.

All collected data were entered and analyzed using SPSS version 22. Numerical variables, such as gestational age, were presented as mean \pm standard deviation. Categorical variables, including gender, feeding practice (exclusive breastfeeding or bottle-feeding), and presence of bronchiolitis, were presented as frequencies and percentages. Data were

stratified for gestational age and gender to control for potential effect modifiers. After stratification, the chi-square test was applied, and a p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant. The frequency of bronchiolitis was compared between breastfed and bottle-fed infants using the chi-square test.

RESULTS:

Table 1 shows the baseline characteristics of the study population consisting of 312 infants. The age distribution ranged from 6 to 12 months, with the largest group being 9 months old (17.6%, 95% CI: 13.5–21.7) followed by 12 months (16.0%, 95% CI: 12.0–20.0). The smallest subgroup was 10 months (11.9%, 95% CI: 8.3–15.5). The overall gender distribution indicated a slight female predominance, with 53.5% (95% CI: 47.9–59.1) females compared to 46.5% (95% CI: 40.9–52.1) males. In terms of feeding practices, the majority were bottle-fed infants, accounting for 72.8% (95% CI: 67.7–77.9), whereas only 27.2% (95% CI: 22.1–32.3) were breastfed. The prevalence of bronchiolitis among the entire cohort was 20.8% (95% CI: 16.3–25.3), with the remaining 79.2% (95% CI: 74.7–83.7) having no evidence of the condition. Table 2 compares the occurrence of bronchiolitis between breastfed and bottle-fed infants. Among breastfed infants (n=85), 13 (15.3%, 95% CI: 8.0–24.6) developed

bronchiolitis, whereas 72 (84.7%) remained unaffected. In contrast, among bottle-fed infants (n=227), bronchiolitis was present in 52 (22.9%, 95% CI: 17.4–28.4) and absent in 175 (77.1%). Although bronchiolitis was more frequent in bottle-fed infants compared to breastfed infants, the difference was not statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 2.173$, $df = 1$, $p = 0.140$).

Table 3 presents stratified analysis of bronchiolitis by feeding type across different age groups and gender. In nearly all age categories (6–12 months), bronchiolitis was consistently more common in bottle-fed infants compared to breastfed infants. For example, at 9 months, 26.8% of bottle-fed infants had bronchiolitis compared to only 7.1% of breastfed infants. At 12 months, the proportion was 34.4% in bottle-fed infants versus 16.7% in breastfed infants. However, none of these age-wise differences reached statistical significance (all $p > 0.05$).

Similarly, when stratified by gender, bronchiolitis remained more frequent in bottle-fed infants. Among males, 22.8% of bottle-fed infants were affected compared to 18.2% of breastfed infants ($p = 0.535$). Among females, 23.0% of bottle-fed infants developed bronchiolitis compared to 12.2% of breastfed infants ($p = 0.135$). These differences also failed to reach statistical significance.

TABLE 1. BASELINE CHARACTERISTICS OF INFANTS (N=312)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percent (%)	95% CI
Age (months)	6	47	15.1	11.1 - 19.1
	7	38	12.2	8.6 - 15.8
	8	44	14.1	10.3 - 17.9
	9	55	17.6	13.5 - 21.7
	10	37	11.9	8.3 - 15.5
	11	41	13.1	9.4 - 16.8
	12	50	16.0	12.0 - 20.0
Gender	Male	145	46.5	40.9 - 52.1
	Female	167	53.5	47.9 - 59.1
Feeding	Breastfed	85	27.2	22.1 - 32.3
	Bottle-fed	227	72.8	67.7 - 77.9
Bronchiolitis	Yes	65	20.8	16.3 - 25.3
	No	247	79.2	74.7 - 83.7

TABLE 2. COMPARISON

N OF BRONCHIOLITIS BY FEEDING TYPE

Feeding Type	Bronchiolitis Yes (n, %)	Bronchiolitis No (n, %)	Total (n)	95% CI
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Breastfed	13 (15.3)	72 (84.7)	85	8.0 - 24.6
Bottle-fed	52 (22.9)	175 (77.1)	227	17.4 - 28.4

Chi-square test: χ^2

= 2.173, df = 1, p = 0.140

TABLE 3. STRATIFICATION OF BRONCHIOLITIS BY FEEDING TYPE, AGE AND GENDER

Stratum	Sub-group	Feeding Type	Bronchiolitis Yes (n, %)	Bronchiolitis No (n, %)	Total (n)	p-value
Age(months)	6	Breastfed	1 (10.0)	9 (90.0)	10	1.000**
		Bottle-fed	5 (13.5)	32 (86.5)	37	
	7	Breastfed	3 (27.3)	8 (72.7)	11	0.932**
		Bottle-fed	7 (25.9)	20 (74.1)	27	
	8	Breastfed	1 (9.1)	10 (90.9)	11	0.475**
		Bottle-fed	6 (18.2)	27 (81.8)	33	
	9	Breastfed	1 (7.1)	13 (92.9)	14	0.124**
		Bottle-fed	11 (26.8)	30 (73.2)	41	
	10	Breastfed	2 (18.2)	9 (81.8)	11	0.431**
		Bottle-fed	8 (30.8)	18 (69.2)	26	
	11	Breastfed	2 (20.0)	8 (80.0)	10	0.581**
		Bottle-fed	4 (12.9)	27 (87.1)	31	
12	Breastfed	3 (16.7)	15 (83.3)	18	0.181**	
	Bottle-fed	11 (34.4)	21 (65.6)	32		
Gender	Male	Breastfed	8 (18.2)	36 (81.8)	44	0.535**
		Bottle-fed	23 (22.8)	78 (77.2)	101	
	Female	Breastfed	5 (12.2)	36 (87.8)	41	0.135**
		Bottle-fed	29 (23.0)	97 (77.0)	126	

*significant

**non-significant

DISCUSSION:

The present study demonstrated that bronchiolitis occurred more frequently in bottle-fed infants (22.9%) compared to breastfed infants (15.3%),

though the difference did not reach statistical significance (p = 0.140). Despite the lack of statistical significance, the consistent trend across age and gender groups suggests that breastfeeding may provide a protective effect against bronchiolitis. This observation is biologically

plausible, as breast milk contains maternal antibodies, immune-modulating factors, and protective nutrients that enhance the infant's defense against viral respiratory infections.

Our findings are in agreement with evidence from international cohorts. Gómez-Acebo et al. reported that exclusive breastfeeding at four months reduced bronchiolitis incidence by 41%, and breastfeeding for at least six months reduced the risk by 55%.¹¹ Similarly, Shikder et al. in Bangladesh observed that exclusive breastfeeding significantly lowered RSV positivity among bronchiolitis patients (OR = 0.127, $p = 0.004$).¹² Both studies strengthen the argument that breastfeeding reduces not only the frequency but also the virologic severity of bronchiolitis.

Environmental and maternal factors also play a substantial role. In Hazara Division, Khan et al. found that surgical delivery, family history of allergies, maternal use of perfume or powder, overcrowded living conditions, and passive smoking were significant contributors to bronchiolitis risk, while breastfeeding provided a degree of protection.¹³ Rustam et al. further reported from Indonesia that non-exclusively breastfed infants were nearly twice as likely to develop upper respiratory tract infections compared to exclusively breastfed infants (OR = 1.69, $p = 0.03$).¹⁴ These findings are consistent with our observation that a higher prevalence of bottle-feeding (72.8%) may be contributing to the burden of bronchiolitis in our population.

On the other hand, results from Saudi Arabia demonstrated that breastfeeding did not significantly influence asthma severity, whereas paternal smoking was strongly predictive of asthma outcome.¹⁵ This indicates that while breastfeeding is effective in reducing acute viral illnesses such as bronchiolitis, chronic airway diseases may be more influenced by genetic predisposition and long-term environmental exposures.

Additional supportive data from Pakistan further emphasize the role of feeding practices in childhood morbidity. Ahmad et al. reported higher rates of pneumonia and acute bronchitis among bottle-fed infants, although these differences were not statistically significant.¹⁶ Irfan et al. showed that breastfed children experienced significantly fewer

respiratory infections, lower rates of sepsis, and reduced ICU admissions compared to formula-fed children.¹⁷ Taken together, these studies illustrate that even when statistical significance is not achieved, breastfeeding consistently demonstrates a protective trend against respiratory illnesses and severe outcomes.

Overall, the body of evidence—including the findings of the current study—supports breastfeeding as an effective protective factor against bronchiolitis and other respiratory infections in infancy. Although our results did not achieve statistical significance, the consistency of trends across local and international studies highlights the need for policies that encourage exclusive breastfeeding during the first six months of life. Future research should focus on larger multicenter cohorts and incorporate environmental and socioeconomic determinants to better define the interaction between feeding practices and respiratory health outcomes in infants.

This study has several important strengths. First, it contributes valuable local evidence from Pakistan, where data on the association between feeding practices and bronchiolitis remain limited. The sample size was adequate ($n = 312$), calculated through the WHO sample size calculator with statistical justification, which enhances the reliability of the results. The study also employed strict operational definitions for breastfeeding, bottle-feeding, and bronchiolitis diagnosis, ensuring uniformity and minimizing diagnostic bias. Another strength lies in the stratification of data by age and gender, which allowed assessment of possible effect modifiers and provided a more detailed understanding of the distribution of bronchiolitis. Moreover, the findings were compared with both regional and international studies, which strengthens external validity and situates the study within the broader scientific literature.

Despite these strengths, the study also has limitations that should be acknowledged. As a single-center hospital-based study, the findings may not be generalizable to the entire population of Pakistan, particularly in rural or resource-limited settings. The cross-sectional design prevents the establishment of causal relationships between feeding type and bronchiolitis, restricting the ability to infer temporality. Additionally, feeding history was based

on maternal recall, which may have introduced recall bias, especially regarding exclusive breastfeeding practices during the first six months of life. Environmental and socioeconomic determinants such as parental smoking, overcrowding, and indoor air pollution, which are known to influence bronchiolitis risk, were not comprehensively evaluated in this study. Finally, although the prevalence of bronchiolitis was consistently higher in bottle-fed infants, the differences did not reach statistical significance, possibly due to limited statistical power to detect small effect sizes.

CONCLUSION:

Breastfeeding demonstrated a protective trend against bronchiolitis compared to bottle-feeding, although the difference was not statistically significant. Bottle-fed infants consistently showed a higher frequency of bronchiolitis across different subgroups. These findings highlight the importance of promoting exclusive breastfeeding during the first six months of life as a preventive measure against respiratory illnesses. To strengthen the evidence base, future research should include multicenter, prospective studies with larger sample sizes and careful assessment of environmental and socioeconomic risk factors.

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